

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AT THE UNIVERSITY

Baymetov Mukhammatali Mehriddinovich

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Lecturer at the Department of Technological Education

jaxongir.butunov@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902692>

ANNOTATION

The state describes the role of practical training in the educational process in pedagogical universities and the development of ways to improve the effectiveness of practice.

Key words: practice, student, professional skills, practical supervisor, development, efficiency, work, independent.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье описывается роль практики в образовательном процессе в педагогических вузах и разработка путей повышения эффективности практики.

Ключевые слова: практика, студент, профессиональные навыки, практический руководитель, развитие, эффективность, работа, самостоятельная.

ANNOTATSIYA

Davlat pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida o'quv jarayonidagi amaliy mashg'ulotlarning o'rni va amaliyot samaradorligini oshirish yo'llarini ishlab chiqishni tavsiflaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: amaliyot, talaba, kasbiy mahorat, amaliy rahbar, rivojlanish, samaradorlik, ish, mustaqil.

INTRODUCTION

Educational practices organized in higher educational institutions should be aimed at increasing students' interest in the profession, creative activity and free thinking, independent learning, and the use of modern achievements in science, technology and technology. In our opinion, it is important to study the influence of educational practices on the educational process.

In the process of educational practice, students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities that meet general requirements, and they must be adapted to the impact of scientific and technological changes. Acquired knowledge, skills and competencies form the basis of professional knowledge, and their consistency determines the effectiveness of practice. At the same time, the knowledge, skills and qualifications that students must acquire will depend on their future activities, the type of work and the place they will occupy in production.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The process of basic education serves as the basis of special education, so the student must have a solid theoretical and practical background in these subjects.

The basic education process serves as the basis for special education, therefore, the student should have solid theoretical and practical training in the specified subjects. [1]

The process of educational practice - the practice is carried out according to the orientation to the chosen profession and must meet the requirements of technical and technological development in this field, but the practice program developed in a centralized manner cannot

meet the requirements of educational institutions or enterprises, because if one type of technological equipment is studied in one field, then in another type it is preferable to conduct educational practice in various fields in the preparation of specialists. In this process, it is necessary to ensure that in the process of clearly and perfectly introducing students to the features of the educational institution or enterprise, they can apply the knowledge and skills acquired in all types of work in the educational institution or enterprise. Students should be able to apply knowledge about technical and technological processes, devices and equipment in educational practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this process, the practice manager should achieve the following: teach the student to work with modern technical processes and modern methods and devices; the method of labor organization is to organize educational practices that meet the requirements of modern technology to perform various work operations depending on the student's necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications, professional qualifications; teaching the student to approach the performance of work standards; training in the correct reading of working drawings and the correct use of technological documents in an educational institution or enterprise; use of student work as important training in an educational institution or enterprise team; teaching the student to follow labor, production and fire safety requirements; instilling in the mind of the student a sense of responsibility and appreciation for the workplace and work tools; to give the student an impression of the work culture, to teach the correct organization of the workplace. [2]

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In general, today, it is necessary to train such specialist personnel that they can consciously contribute to the increase of work productivity. It is necessary to educate them in the spirit of increasing the reputation of the educational institution or the enterprise where they work, the quality of work, and strict observance of labor discipline.

During the preparatory period, students get acquainted with specific types of work and solve the following issues: organization of the workplace, compliance with labor safety, discipline in educational practice, maintenance of work tools, compliance with personal hygiene and sanitary rules, etc. The tasks of the students are to study the technical documents during the work process, adjust the devices, prepare the workplace for work, check the quality of the developed product, they study simple work processes.

During the period of mastery of the profession, after studying the work processes, the acquired knowledge and skills are perfected. For this, such work is selected that the newly established topic and previous ones are covered in the course of work. Then the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of the students will develop.

During the period of supervision and completion, not only the acquired knowledge and skills are strengthened, but also they are perfected using modern equipment and devices. Studying and mastering the works of industrial pioneers and veterans helps the student to develop a sense of independence in the process of educational practice. They enter the flow of the labor team, are educated in the team and are formed as individuals.

Personal qualities of practice leaders that provide the human factor in the process of educational practice: demandingness and justice, selflessness and honesty, benevolence, enterprisingness, sense of humor and seriousness. These qualities raise them to the level of a teacher, increase their prestige in front of students, their teaching and upbringing.

has a positive effect on the acquisition skill. The ability to objectively control and evaluate the knowledge and skills of future technological education teachers is the resulting quality indicator that determines the effectiveness of the production practice process. Practice supervisors should have excellent knowledge of objective and subjective methods of monitoring students' knowledge, be able to use them, and have the ability to introduce a rating system. Based on existing research, it is possible to describe the important professional qualities of practice managers of higher educational institutions from the point of view of a scientist, pedagogue, educator:

Educational-pedagogical activities are directed to the organization of the educational process. As in all pedagogic higher education institutions, the educational process is characterized by the integration of educational and research aspects, ensuring the activity and independence of students, as well as their creative potential as individuals. In the work of a pedagogue, there is a practical activity aimed at creating theoretical and specific situations related to the discovery of new laws, solving the system of pedagogical tasks. The teacher determines the goals and tasks of teaching on a specific subject, selects the content of teaching, chooses active methods in accordance with the students' cognitive activity, and determines the theoretical type. [3]

Today, higher education institutions are an important link in the development of a well-rounded person, a qualified specialist. Their practice process is provided with advanced, modern equipment and educational equipment, qualified teaching staff. This plays an important role in increasing the efficiency of production practices. Production practice is carried out to prepare future teachers of technological education for the conscious and careful study of general and special subjects by profession, to acquire practical professional competence and skills in the chosen specialty. As a rule, production practices are conducted by practice leaders. The list of production practices is determined by the higher education institution

CONCLUSION:

At the end of the production practice, the student defends his report before the commission appointed by the higher education institution. The grade of the production practice result is taken into account when the student moves from course to course. The end of the internship is discussed in the methodological council of the higher education institution. The scientific council of the higher educational institution will finalize the results of the practice. A student who has not completed the internship program, received an unsatisfactory review of his work or an unsatisfactory grade in the defense of the report, will be sent to re-internship at his own expense during the vacation.

The work completed in the prescribed manner is submitted by the student to the supervisor.[4] After making sure that the work has been completed to the required level, the leader presents the work with his review to the head of the department. In the review, based on the student's activity, news of the adopted decisions and other positive materials of the case, a decision is made about including the case for defense by the student. If the head of the department considers that the student's work cannot be included in the defense, the issue will be discussed at the meeting of the department with the participation of the head..

References:

1. Baymetov M.M. (2021) Ways to improve the organization and effectiveness of educational practices in vocational schools. – Academic Research in Educational Sciences, VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4 | 2021 1190-1195.
2. Baymetov M.M. Didactic principles of ensuring the integration of educational and production practices. - My teacher is constantly educating. #1/1 2022.
3. Khamidov J.A., Baymetov M.M. Theoretical and methodological bases of providing a production process cluster with practices in vocational schools.
4. "Economics and Society" No. 12(91) 20214. Khamidov J.A. "O nekotorykh vormax metodax trudovogo vospitaniya mladshikh shkolnikov". – Academic Research in Educational Sciences #2(81)2021